

Concentrations of some metals in sediment, *Macrobrachium macrobrachion*, and *Tympanotonus fuscatus* obtained from the Great Kwa River, Calabar, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to determine the concentrations of some metals in sediment and flesh of *Macrobrachium macrobrachion* and *Tympanotonus fuscatus* obtained from the Great Kwa River, Calabar, Nigeria. Sampling and analyses were done between June and September, 2014 and the samples were collected from three sampling locations (location 1: Esuk Ekpoeyo; location 2: Esuk Atu; location 3: Obufa Esuk). The analysis was done through the buck scientific atomic absorption spectrophotometer model VGP210 after digestion of the samples. The concentration values obtained across the different sampling locations and between specimens were recorded. Mean concentration values of metals in sediment were: cadmium (Cd), 0.129±0.045 mg/kg; chromium (Cr), 0.112±0.020 mg/kg; copper (Cu), 0.061±0.012 mg/kg; manganese (Mn), 0.038±0.004 mg/kg; nickel (Ni), 0.062±0.006 mg/kg; lead (Pb), 0.143±0.047 mg/kg and zinc (Zn), 0.088±0.014 mg/kg. The concentration values of metals recorded in *M. macrobrachion* were: Cd, 0.0076±0.001 mg/kg; Cr, 0.016±0.005 mg/kg; Cu, 0.033±0.002 mg/kg; Mn, 0.02±0.001 mg/kg; Ni, 0.005±0.005 mg/kg; Pb, 0.032±0.002 mg/kg and Zn, 0.037±0.02 mg/kg while the values in *T. fuscatus*, were: Cd, 0.008±0.006 mg/kg; Cr, 0.017±0.004 mg/kg; Cu, 0.024±0.004 mg/kg; Mn, 0.023±0.0015 mg/kg; Ni, 0.008±0.006 mg/kg; Pb, 0.119±0.176 mg/kg and Zn, 0.035±0.017 mg/kg. There was no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) in the concentrations of metals across stations (1-3) and amongst samples (sediment, *M. macrobrachion* and *T. fuscatus*). The concentrations of some metals in the samples were below acceptable limits except Cr which was slightly higher in all the samples, Cd and Ni in sediment, Cu in *M. macrobrachion* and Pb in *T. fuscatus*. This suggests that there is a slight deviation from the acceptable limit of metals in benthos from the Great Kwa River and the sediment is moderately unhealthy to support aquatic biota. However, activities resulting to anthropogenic input of metals in the Great Kwa River should be prohibited in order to avoid possible deleterious effects of these metals after a long period of accumulation.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Human activities play a major role in the introduction of various anthropogenic pollutants in surface waters. Among the pollutants are heavy metals which are at the beginning considered as natural elements, essential to the

development of living organisms with very weak concentration where as a high concentration of these elements become toxic. These anthropogenic pollutants in surface waters results in high concentration of heavy metals which lower water quality and at the same time accumulate in the sediment and benthos like

mollusc, arthropods and other benthic communities. The pollutants have varying sources which includes industrial, urban waste discharges, sewage disposal, run-offs, agricultural leached chemicals, thermal sources, radioactive wastes etc. All these important factors and modify water and sediment compositions, thus affecting the benthic communities and other aquatic organisms.

Heavy metal pollution of the aquatic ecosystem and even the terrestrial environment have been of environmental concern ever since and this is largely because they are not biologically degradable and as such accumulate in the tissues of plants and animals as well. This implies that bioaccumulation of these heavy metals increase their level of pollution which creates public health problems as they are transferred through food chains or web to man's consumption. Many aquatic organisms for examples prawns (*Macrobrachium macrobrachion*) and periwinkles (*Tympanotonus Fuscatus*) have the ability to accumulate and biomagnify contaminants like heavy metals, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in the environments. Periwinkles are mass consumer product constituting relatively cheap animal protein in Delta state [1] and are one of the many delicacies in Nigeria. The ingestion of these contaminants may affect not only the productivity and productive capacities of these organisms, but ultimately affect the health of man that depends on these organisms as a major source of protein. The periwinkle (*Tympanotonus fuscatus*) is a mollusc of high economic value; it is a deposit feeder and bio-indicator of heavy metals and hydrocarbon pollutions in the aquatic environment. It is of vital importance, hence studies are conducted to ascertain the level of concentration of metals in the commercial species [2,3] and determine potentially hazardous levels for human. Heavy metals accumulation adversely affects various biological processes like reproduction, feeding, growth, maturity and so on. Therefore, it is important to always determine the bioaccumulation capacity for heavy metals by organisms, especially edible ones like prawns, periwinkle and other aquatic organisms in order to assess and ascertain potential risks to human health. Prawns are an important food source for larger animals from fish to whales. As with other sea food, prawns are high in calcium, iodine and protein but low in food energy. Consumption of prawns from rivers and streams polluted by heavy metals by humans is thought to lead to disorders or diseases like: Liver dysfunction, Parkinson's disease, heart failure, decreased fertility, still births, some types of cancers, poisoning etc. These metals don't readily breakdown in the environment [4].

Metals can cause serious health effects with varied symptoms depending on the nature and quantity of metal ingested [5]. The most common metals that humans are exposed to are: aluminium, arsenic, cadmium, lead and mercury. Aluminium has been associated with

Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease, senility and pre-senile dementia. Arsenic exposure can cause among other illnesses or symptoms, cancer, abdominal pain and skin lesions. Cadmium exposure produces kidney damage and hypertension. Lead is a cumulative poison and a possible human carcinogen [6] while for mercury, toxicity results in mental disturbance and impairment of speech, hearing, vision and movement [7]. In addition, lead and mercury may cause the development of autoimmunity in which a person's immune system attacks its own cells. This can lead to joint diseases and ailment of the kidneys and circulatory system and neurons. At high concentrations, lead and mercury can cause irreversible brain damage.

Heavy metals found in natural water bodies occur at varying concentrations and are usually monitored by measuring their concentrations in water, sediment and biota. Aquatic organisms can acquire these heavy metals from food, suspended particles or directly from the water. Many aquatic organisms have been used as sensitive indicators of heavy metal pollution [8,9]. Biota that inhabit contaminated sites are generally exposed to very high concentrations of the pollutants [10].

The Great Kwa River runs through farmlands, industrial, commercial and recreational areas such as obufa Esuk, Esuk Atu, Calabar Free Trade Zone, Teaching Hospital, University of Calabar, Satellite Town and Peri-urban areas before it finally enters Calabar Estuary. Calabar Municipality has no waste treatment facilities, and heavy rains wash human and industrial wastes into the river. Despite increasing anthropogenic influences due to the rapid development of Calabar town in recent times, there is dearth of information regarding the concentrations of metals in benthos and sediment from the Great Kwa River. This research is aimed at measuring the concentrations of some metals in prawn (*Macrobrachium macrobrachion*), periwinkle (*Tympanotonus fuscatus*) and sediment from the Great Kwa River, Calabar, Nigeria. The results obtained were compared to the World Health Organisation (WHO) and Federal Ministry of Environment (FMENV) to ascertain whether the metals exceeded the threshold limits in the organisms and environment.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Description of the study area

The Great Kwa River flows through Cross River State, Nigeria, draining the east side of the city of Calabar. It is located between latitude 8° 15'E and 8° 30'E and longitude 4° 45'N and 5° 15'N. It has an estimated length of 56km and is about 2.8km wide. The river originates in the Oban Hill, in the Cross River National Park, and flows southwards to the Cross River estuary. Two climatic seasons (wet and dry) prevail in the study area. The wet season is characterized by

high rainfall while the dry season experiences occasional downpours. The shorelines are lined

with dark mud plates usually exposed during low tides, the water at the shore being brackish

and rich in macro-invertebrates, fish fauna and debris. The banks are also surrounded by Lush evergreen forest vegetation with different species of trees, shrubs and grasses. The river ecology is under threat from human activities. Human activities such as farming on the adjoining lands, aquaculture and artisanal fisheries have created some ecological impacts in the river. However, Calabar is growing, due in part to the Calabae Free Trade Zone, causing growing numbers of houses and factories to be built in the freshwater and mangrove swamps of the Great Kwa.

2.2 Sampling locations

For the purpose of this study, samples were collected from three (3) different sampling locations established along the length of the Great Kwa River and spread out for effective

sampling and maximum results with the distance of about 3.5 km from Esuk Ekpo Eyo to Esuk Atu and about 2 km from Esuk Atu to Obufa Esuk. Therefore a total of 5.5 km was covered along the length of the Great Kwa River.

Location 1: This station is located at Esuk Ekpo Eyo Community. It is called Akpabuyo Beach by the residents of Akpabuyo L.G.A. of Cross River State. It situates between longitude 8° 23' 23.6" E and latitude 4° 56' 53.5"N. A bridge is built across the river here to allow passage of vehicles and people. The river in this station is highly turbid and no observable unidirectional flow of the water at this station due to the very wide nature of the river, thus surface current is not very distinct to determine. Grasses are observed along the bank of the river at this

station. Major human activities in this station include sand mining, boat building while fishing is sparingly practiced by residents of the area.

Location 2: This station is located at Esuk Atu, close to the biological science block and teaching hospital areas of the University of Calabar. It situates between longitude $8^{\circ} 21' 50.6''$ E and latitude $4^{\circ} 57' 19.9''$ N. The bed of the River at this station is covered by smooth sand and mud and turbidity is high here. The river here is swift flowing, the vegetation here include palm trees, fan palm (*Hyphaena petersiana*) and elephant grasses. Human activities here are mainly fishing (artisanal fishery) and small scale farming.

Location 3: This station is located at Esuk Orok (Obufa Esuk), which is close to the University of Calabar staff quarters. It situates between longitude $8^{\circ} 21' 17.4''$ E and latitude $4^{\circ} 56' 57.9''$ N. The bed of the river at this station is covered by mud or clay and the water is highly turbid. Due to the very wide nature of the river, there is no observable unidirectional flow of the water, thus the surface current is not very distinct to be determined. Vegetation here include fan palm (*Hyphaena petersiana*) and grasses. Major human activities here are fishing (artisanal fishery) and small scale farming.

2.3 Collection of Samples

The study was done for a period of 4 months between June and September, 2014. Sediment and Live periwinkle (*T. fuscatus*) and prawn (*M. macrobrachion*) were sampled from all 3 stations. *T. fuscatus* and *M. macrobrachion* were directly purchased randomly from the local fishermen who collected them while sediment was carefully collected from the river bottom within the sampling locations. The specimens were rinsed with the river water to remove debris and wrapped in cellophane bags and labelled accordingly and kept in a cooler containing ice blocks during transportation to the laboratory for analysis.

2.4 Preparation and analysis of the samples

The samples were separated accordingly and washed with distilled water to remove all dirt and then drained. All samples washed were placed in a petri-dish and labelled accordingly and oven dried at 80°C . The dried samples were then ground in glass mortar and pestle to very fine particles. To a beaker containing 1g each of the samples, 30ml of perchloric acid and concentrated nitric acid were added and then placed on the digestion heater until the organic matter were broken down which was observed through the reduced volume and clarity of the solution. After cooling, the digested samples were transferred to a 100ml standard (STD) flask and were filled up to mark with distilled water. The diluted samples were transferred to sample bottles and labelled accordingly. The total metals (Cd, Cr, Cu, Mn, Ni, Pb and Zn)

concentrations of the samples were then determined in triplicate using the desired hollow cathode lamp in the Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS); model; VGP210 Buck Scientific.

2.5 Statistical analysis

The data obtained were subjected to descriptive statistics for mean and standard deviation (S.D) and presented in tables. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was employed to determine the significant difference between stations (1 to 3) and amongst species.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Metals Concentrations in sediment

The mean and range values of metals in sediment is presented in Table 1. Lead (Pb) has the highest mean value (0.143 ± 0.047) with range values of 0.000-0.338 followed by Cd (0.129 ± 0.045) with range values of 0.018-0.398 and the least is Mn (0.038 ± 0.004) with range values of 0.015-0.061. The mean values of the metals in the descending order of magnitude are $\text{Pb} > \text{Cd} > \text{Cr} > \text{Zn} > \text{Ni} > \text{Cu} > \text{Mn}$.

3.2 Metals Concentrations in *M. Macrobrachion*

Results of metals concentrations in *M. macrobrachion* are shown in table 2. Cadmium (Cd) ranged from 0.00-0.02mg/kg with mean and standard deviation values of 0.008 ± 0.001 across the sampling locations. The mean value is lower than the standard levels of the World Health Organisation (WHO). Concentration value of Cr is ranged between 0.01-0.02 with mean and standard deviation values of 0.016 ± 0.005 across the sampling locations. The metal concentration slightly exceeded the standard level of WHO. Cu ranged between 0.031-0.035mg/kg with the mean and standard deviation values of 0.033 ± 0.002 across the sampling locations. The concentration value was observed to fall below the standard levels of WHO. Concentration values of Mn ranged between 0.021-0.023mg/kg with mean and standard deviation values of 0.021 ± 0.001 across the sampling locations. The concentration level of this metal is below the standard values of WHO. Ni ranged between 0.000-0.010mg/kg with mean and standard deviation values of 0.0053 ± 0.005 across sampling locations. Nickel concentration levels falls below the standard levels of WHO. Pb values ranged between 0.031-0.035mg/kg with mean and standard deviation values of 0.32 ± 0.002 across the sampling locations. From this study it was observed that the values of Lead were higher than the standard levels of WHO. Zn ranged between 0.035-0.037mg/kg with mean and standard deviation values of 0.037 ± 0.002 across the sampling locations. The values of Zn were lower than the standard levels of WHO of 3.0mg/kg and FMENV of $< 3.0\text{mg/kg}$.

The concentrations of these metals in *M. macrobrachion* obtained from the Great Kwa River is in this descending order

Zn>Cu>Pb>Mn>Cr>Cd>Ni. Zn concentration is the highest although still within safety limits of WHO while Ni showed the lowest concentration.

Table 1. Concentrations of some metals in sediment samples from the Great Kwa River, Calabar

Metals	Mean±S.D	Range	WHO Std
Cd (mg/kg)	0.129±0.045	0.018-0.398	<0.01
Cr (mg/kg)	0.112±0.020	0.000-0.240	<0.01
Cu (mg/kg)	0.061±0.012	0.014-0.780	0.1
Mn (mg/kg)	0.038±0.004	0.015-0.061	5.0
Ni (mg/kg)	0.062±0.006	0.000-0.094	0.02
Pb (mg/kg)	0.143±0.047	0.000-0.338	0.05
Zn (mg/kg)	0.088±0.014	0.016-0.161	3.0

Table 2. Concentrations of some metals in *M. macrobrachion* from the Great Kwa River, Calabar

Metals	Mean±S.D	Range	WHO Std
Cd (mg/kg)	0.008±0.001	0.00-0.020	<0.01
Cr (mg/kg)	0.016±0.005	0.01-0.020	<0.01
Cu (mg/kg)	0.033±0.002	0.031-0.035	0.1
Mn (mg/kg)	0.021±0.001	0.021-0.023	5.0
Ni (mg/kg)	0.005±0.005	0.00-0.010	0.02
Pb (mg/kg)	0.032±0.002	0.031-0.035	0.05
Zn (mg/kg)	0.037±0.020	0.035-0.037	3.0

WHO = World Health Organisation, FMENV= Federal Ministry of Environment Std = Standards, S.D= Standard Deviation

Table 3. Concentrations of some metals in *T. fuscatus* from the Great Kwa River, Calabar

Metals	Mean±S.D	Range	WHO Std
Cd (mg/kg)	0.008±0.006	0.002-0.015	<0.01
Cr (mg/kg)	0.017±0.004	0.013-0.021	<0.01
Cu (mg/kg)	0.024±0.004	0.020-0.028	0.1
Mn (mg/kg)	0.023±0.0015	0.022-0.025	5.0
Ni (mg/kg)	0.008±0.006	0.00-0.012	0.02
Pb (mg/kg)	0.119±0.176	0.003-0.321	0.05
Zn(mg/kg)	0.035±0.017	0.033-0.036	3.0

3.3 Metals Concentrations in *T. Fuscatus*

The summary of the metals concentrations in *T. Fuscatus* is shown in Tables 3. Cd values ranged between 0.002-0.015 mg/kg with mean and standard deviation values of 0.008 ± 0.006 across the sampling locations. Using these observed values, Cadmium levels of concentration from this study is lower than the standard levels laid down by WHO. Cr ranged from 0.013 – 0.021 mg/kg with mean and standard deviation values of 0.017 ± 0.004 across the sampling locations. From the values observed, chromium slightly exceeded the

standard levels (0.01mg/kg) set by WHO. Cu concentration levels ranged between 0.02-0.028 mg/kg with mean and standard deviation values of 0.024 ± 0.004 across the sampling locations. The levels of Cu concentration as observed from this study are below hazardous limits of 0.1 mg/kg set by WHO. Mn levels ranged between 0.022-0.025 mg/kg with mean and standard deviation values of 0.023±0.0015 across the sampling locations. The values of Manganese are below the hazardous limit 5.0mg/kg stated by WHO. Ni concentration values ranged between 0.000-0.012mg/kg with mean and standard deviation values of 0.008±0.006

across the sampling locations. The concentration values of Pb ranged between 0.003-0.321 mg/kg with mean and standard deviation values of 0.119 ± 0.176 across the sampling locations. Zinc concentration levels as observed from this study ranged between 0.033-0.036mg/kg with mean and standard deviation values of 0.035 ± 0.017 across the sampling locations. The mean concentration value of Zn is below WHO standard of 3.0 mg/kg.

Concentration values of the metals in *T. fuscatus* obtained from the Great Kwa river in descending order of magnitude are: Pb>Zn>Cu>Mn>Cr>Cd=Ni. Pb has the highest mean value in *T. fuscatus* followed by Zn while Cd and Ni have the lowest mean values.

4. DISCUSSION

Globally, aquatic systems are polluted through anthropogenic activities with chemical pollutants from domestic, agricultural and industrial wastes, which are finally absorbed by aquatic plants and animals. According to [11], heavy metal pollution in aquatic systems is an important environmental problem, since heavy metals are among some of the most dangerous toxicants that bioaccumulate in aquatic plant and animal tissues. Results obtained in this study shows that some heavy metals including Cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), Chromium (Cr), Nickel (Ni), Copper (Cu), Zinc (Zn) and Manganese (Mn) were present in the sediment and benthos from the three sampling stations of the Great Kwa River. [12] reported that the consumption of food such as fish with high levels of heavy metals such as lead (Pb), can induce convulsion, abdominal pains, drowsiness, vomiting, kidney and reproductive system malfunction in humans. In pollution studies, sediment quality is used as an indicator by contaminants including trace metals because it provides a deeper insight into the long-term pollution state of the aquatic environment [13]. Sediment being the loose sand, clay, silt and other soil particles which settle at the bottom of body of water [14] is a major habitat and major nutrient source for aquatic organisms such as fish, micro-invertebrates and macro-invertebrates [15]. Sediments have been described as a ready sink of pollutants where they concentrate according to the levels of pollution [16]. However, the occurrence of heavy metals such as Cd, Pb, Cr, Ni, Cu, Zn and Mn in the sediments of the Great Kwa River may be attributed to farming activities on the shore of the river where pesticides and other agrochemicals are utilized to increase productivity. Contaminations of heavy metals in the sediment from the Great Kwa River obtained in this study were in the following order: Pb>Cd>Cr>Zn>Cu>Ni>Mn. This findings disagrees with [13] which reported the following order (Ni>Fe>Pb>Mn>Zn>Co>Hg) for trace metals in the surface sediment of Ona River, Western Nigeria. The variations could be as a result of differences in the anthropogenic activities which take place in the different locations. In this study, the concentrations of

heavy metals in the sediments were moderate indicating a moderate level of anthropogenic activities in the River Locality. Some of the metals concentrations recorded in this study were below WHO average levels for rivers and soils. Concentration of lead (Pb) which was highest in this study in Great Kwa River sediments has a serious environmental concern. According to [17], Pb enters children bloodstream more than adults when Pb-contaminated fish is consumed. [13] attributed this to the higher rate of detoxification ($\approx 99\%$) of the metal in adult and elimination through urine and faeces than in children (65%). Cadmium which was second in the order of metals concentrations in this study was present in all the samples and was higher than the concentrations of Cd found in sediments from Abuloma River (0.118 mg/kg) and Itu river (0.106mg/kg) reported by [12]. [18] attributed this to pollutants from industrial and agricultural processes. According to Järup (2003) [19], bioaccumulation of Cd results in kidney damage and can also cause a disease condition known as Osteomalacia. Results obtained from Zn indicate that Zn Concentrations were below WHO acceptable limit. This observation is similar to findings of other authors such as [19] in sediments of Akpe Yafe River, [20] in sediment of major dams in Ekiti State, [13] for Ona river, [12] for Abuloma and Itu River.

The contamination of metals in sediments and biota is of major concern especially in many industrialized countries because of their toxicity, persistence and bioaccumulative nature [21]. The average values of Cd, Cr, Cu, Mn, Ni, Pb and Zn for both *M. macrobrachion* and *T. fuscatus* in this study agreed with the corresponding values obtained by [22] in Lake Qarun, except for Cr which corresponds with the acceptable limit of World Health Organisation [23], but from this study Cr was found to be higher than the acceptable standard of World Health Organisation (WHO). The presence of trace metals in Great Kwa River is mainly of allochthonous origin due to either agricultural influx, wastes of fish farms or sewage via surrounding cultivated lands. The levels of Chromium and Cadmium in this study could be attributed to farming activities which entails the use of manures, pesticides and fertilizers which enter the river through run-off from the surround areas. Dumping and burning of domestic waste by residents of these locations and effluent from cement industry located not within the sampling area can also constitute input of metals in the river. The introduction of Pb which showed high concentration in these locations is as a result of small scale farming which introduces fertilizers into the river and emissions from increased motorised boats and automobiles. Trace elements in waters may be undergoing rapid changes affecting the rate of uptake or release by sediments, thus influencing living organisms throughout the water-sediment interaction chain [24]. Although, some of these metals are classified biochemically as essential elements in the bodies of living organisms and aquatic

plants when present in trace amounts e.g. (Cr, Cu and Ni) but, when they are present in high concentrations, may become toxic [25]. In addition, the pollutant concentrations in the organism are the result of the past as well as recent contamination level of the environment in which the organism lives, while the pollutants concentrations in the water only indicate the situation at the time of sampling [26]. From the large volume of water they filter, molluscs (*T. fuscatus*) take up and accumulate in their bodies toxic metals without noxious effects [27]. The results of current study indicate that Molluscs have the highest concentrations of most trace metals measured. These were in concordance with the findings of [28] who reported that, Molluscs (*T. fuscatus*) in Al-Hodeidah region (Yemen) appears to be useful tool as a bio-indicator for most of the metals. Trace metals tend to accumulate in different body organs. These metals are dangerous for these organisms and in turn they lead to serious problems in both man and animals [29].

5. CONCLUSION

This study measured the concentration the Mn, Cr, Hg, Cd, Pb, Zn, Cu, and Ni in sediment, *M. macrobrachion* and *T. fuscatus* from the Great Kwa River, Calabar. Data from sediments of the Great Kwa River has provided information on the impact of human activities on the river. The concentrations of some metals in the samples were below acceptable limits except Cr which was slightly higher in all the samples, Cd and Ni in sediment, Cu in *M. macrobrachion* and Pb in *T. fuscatus*. This suggests that there is a slight deviation from the acceptable limit of metals in benthos from the Great Kwa River and the sediment is moderately unhealthy to support aquatic biota.

However, activities resulting to anthropogenic input of metals in the Great Kwa River should be prohibited in order to avoid possible deleterious effects of these metals after a long period of accumulation. This will reduce environmental risks and human health risks, as the prolonged exposure of these metals could amount to great health hazards. Prolonged exposure to Chromium through ingestion of food high in Chromium could lead to severe damages to vital human systems, such as the immunological systems, reproductive systems and other developmental problems, also high exposure to Cadmium result in diarrhoea, severe abdominal pains and vomiting, weakening of the bones and damages to the kidney, high concentration of Lead (Pb) taken from aquatic foods could result in several problems or health hazards like high blood pressure, reproductive problems, hearing and vision impairment, liver and kidney damage.

Prolonged consumption of high quantities of *M. macrobrachion* and *T. fuscatus* from the Great Kwa River could pose some health risks, therefore constant monitoring of metals concentrations in this river could be useful and activities around the river should also be

monitored to reduce the influx of metals. This study may provide preliminary data for the future research on concentration of metals in the Great Kwa River.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

KAO designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. UPE and SO carried out the field sampling, managed the literature searches and the analyses of the study. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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